

PROGNOSTIC ROLE OF NEUTROPHIL-LYMPHOCYTE RATIO AND TRIGLYCERIDE-GLUCOSE INDEX IN ASSESSING MYOCARDIAL DYSFUNCTION SEVERITY AMONG STEMI PATIENTS**Dr. Victor Thomas V.^{*1}, Dr. Gurushanthappa S.², Dr. Harisha E. J.³**^{*1}Postgraduate Student, Department of General Medicine, J. J.M. Medical College, Davangere, Karnataka.²Professor, Department of General Medicine, J. J.M. Medical College, Davangere, Karnataka.³Professor and Head, Department of General Medicine, J. J.M. Medical College, Davangere, Karnataka.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Victor Thomas V.**

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ABSTRACT

This retrospective, single-centre study aimed to evaluate the prognostic significance of the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) and triglyceride-glucose (TyG) index in patients with ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) and to explore their correlation with the Global Registry of Acute Coronary Events (GRACE) risk score. A total of 152 confirmed STEMI patients were included. Clinical, hematological, and biochemical data were collected, and NLR was calculated as neutrophil/lymphocyte count, while the TyG index was computed as $\ln[\text{fasting triglycerides (mg/dL)} \times \text{fasting glucose (mg/dL)} / 2]$. Cardiac function was assessed by echocardiography, and statistical analysis was performed using SPSS v25. The mean age of the study population was 45 ± 28 years, with males comprising 81.6%. The average NLR was 6.83 ± 4.08 , TyG index 8.99 ± 0.47 , and mean ejection fraction $42.9 \pm 7.25\%$. NLR showed a significant positive correlation with the GRACE risk score ($r = 0.269$, $p = 0.02$), indicating its strong prognostic value as an inflammatory biomarker in STEMI. Although the TyG index exhibited a positive but non-significant correlation, it suggests potential clinical relevance. Incorporating these simple, inexpensive biomarkers into standard evaluation may enhance early risk stratification and guide individualized management of STEMI patients.

KEYWORDS: STEMI, neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio, triglyceride-glucose index, GRACE risk score, cardiac dysfunction.**INTRODUCTION**

Acute ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) is one of the most serious and life-threatening cardiovascular emergencies, usually resulting from acute coronary artery occlusion due to rupture or erosion of an atherosclerotic plaque followed by thrombosis.^[1] Despite advances in reperfusion strategies and pharmacological therapy, STEMI continues to be associated with significant morbidity, mortality, and long-term adverse cardiovascular outcomes.^[2] Understanding the underlying mechanisms and identifying novel prognostic markers for risk stratification remain key priorities in improving patient care and outcomes.^[2] Atherosclerosis, the fundamental pathology underlying STEMI, is a complex process influenced by dyslipidaemia, inflammation, and insulin resistance (IR).^[3] Insulin

resistance is increasingly recognized as an important metabolic risk factor contributing to coronary atherosclerosis.^[4] By reducing cellular sensitivity to the metabolic actions of insulin, IR disrupts glucose and lipid homeostasis, leading to hyperglycaemia, elevated triglycerides, and other metabolic abnormalities that accelerate vascular damage.^[5] Moreover, IR promotes the development and progression of atherosclerosis by initiating a proinflammatory milieu, endothelial dysfunction, vasoconstriction, and a prothrombotic state.^[6]

Although the hyperinsulinemic euglycemic clamp (HIEC) remains the reference method to measure insulin resistance, its invasive nature and high cost restrict its application in routine practice.^[7] In this context, the

triglyceride-glucose (TyG) index, calculated from fasting triglyceride and glucose levels, has emerged as a simple, inexpensive, and reliable surrogate marker of Insulin Resistance.^[8] Several studies have validated the strong correlation between the TyG index and HIEC-derived IR, highlighting its clinical applicability.^[7,8] Importantly, recent research has demonstrated that elevated TyG index levels are associated with adverse cardiovascular events, poor prognosis, and increased severity of coronary atherosclerosis in STEMI patients. This emphasizes the potential role of the TyG index as a valuable biomarker for risk stratification in acute coronary syndromes.^[8]

In addition to metabolic derangements, inflammation is a central player in the initiation, progression, and complications of atherosclerosis.^[9] Neutrophils and lymphocytes are among the most important inflammatory cells involved in the pathophysiology of STEMI. During an acute myocardial infarction, there is massive recruitment of neutrophils to the infarct site, leading to the release of proteolytic enzymes, inflammatory mediators, and reactive oxygen species (ROS), which exacerbate myocardial injury and propagate inflammation. Conversely, lymphocytes, particularly regulatory subsets, exert protective anti-inflammatory effects. Thus, the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR), a simple measure derived from routine complete blood counts, has gained attention as an integrated marker reflecting the balance between proinflammatory and regulatory immune responses.^[10]

Previous studies have consistently demonstrated that elevated NLR is associated with worse clinical outcomes in patients with acute coronary syndromes, including STEMI.^[11] High NLR levels have been correlated with greater coronary artery disease burden, larger infarct size, impaired left ventricular function, higher in-hospital mortality, and an increased incidence of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE).^[12] Therefore, NLR has emerged as a promising biomarker for assessing disease severity, risk stratification, and prognosis in acute myocardial infarction.^[13]

The Global Registry of Acute Coronary Events (GRACE) risk score is one of the most widely used and validated tools for predicting short- and long-term outcomes in patients with acute coronary syndromes. It incorporates variables such as age, heart rate, systolic blood pressure, serum creatinine, Killip class, ST-segment deviation, cardiac arrest, and troponin levels to provide a comprehensive risk assessment.^[14,15,16] However, integrating simple inflammatory and metabolic

biomarkers such as NLR and the TyG index with the GRACE score may further enhance its predictive accuracy and clinical utility.^[16]

This study aimed to evaluate the association of the triglyceride–glucose (TyG) index and the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) with the severity of cardiac dysfunction in patients with ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI), and to further examine their relationship with the Global Registry of Acute Coronary Events (GRACE) risk score.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

After obtaining prior clearance from the Institutional Ethical Committee, this retrospective, single-centre study was conducted using hospital records of 152 patients who were admitted with a confirmed diagnosis of ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI). Patient selection was based on documented clinical features, electrocardiographic findings, and biochemical evidence consistent with STEMI. Demographic details, relevant medical history including comorbid conditions, laboratory parameters, and treatment details were systematically collected from medical records. For each patient, the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) and the triglyceride–glucose (TyG) index were calculated as biomarkers of systemic inflammation and insulin resistance, respectively. The TyG index was computed using the formula:

$$\text{TyG} = \ln [\text{fasting triglycerides (mg/dL)} \times \text{fasting plasma glucose (mg/dL)} / 2], \text{ while the NLR was derived as } \text{NLR} = \text{neutrophil count } (\times 10^9 / \text{L}) / \text{lymphocyte count } (\times 10^9 / \text{L}).$$

The severity of cardiac dysfunction was assessed using echocardiographic parameters and classified accordingly. In addition, the Global Registry of Acute Coronary Events (GRACE) risk score was calculated for all patients to stratify clinical risk.

Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 25. We summarized continuous variables as mean values with standard deviations and applied paired t-tests to assess group differences and statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

The mean age of the study population was 45 ± 28 years. Among the 152 participants, 124 were males and 28 were females.

Table 1: Hematological parameters of study Population.

Parameters	Mean \pm S.D.
Neutrophil %	76.41 \pm 12.05
Lymphocyte %	15.74 \pm 8.46
Eosinophil %	1.88 \pm 2.74
Monocyte%	5.45 \pm 2.22

Basophil %	0.28 ± 0.21
Absolute neutrophil Count -10 ⁹ /L	8913.33 ±3005.1
Absolute Lymphocyte Count - 10 ⁹ /L	1689.17±821.9
Absolute Eosinophil Count X 10 ⁹ /L	160.83±203.76
Absolute Monocyte Count X 10 ⁹ /L	575.00 ±183
Absolute Basophil Count X 10 ⁹ /L	37.50 ±36.39
Total WBC Count cells /Cu.mm	11407.50 ± 2727.89
Total RBC Count Million /Cu.mm	4.91 ± 0.69
MCV fl	28.68 ± 3.20
MCHC g/dl	87.57 ± 7.73
MCH pg	32.84 ±1.49
PCV %	42.67 ±5.61
Platelet Count Lakhs/Cu.mm	2.54 ±0.74
ESR mm/hour	34 ±12

Table 2: Biochemical parameters and Ejection Fraction of study Population.

Parameters	Mean ± S.D.
Fasting Blood Glucose mg/dL	130.33 ±35.47
Urea mg/dL	27.67 ± 12.29
S. Creatinine mg/dL	0.91 ±0.41
Triglyceride mg/dL	140.82 ±62.83
Total Cholesterol mg/dL	181.33 ± 44.22
HDL mg/dL	43.67 ± 25.99
LDL mg/dL	118.65 ± 44.08
NLR	6.83 ± 4.08
TyG	8.99 ± 0.47
Ejection Fraction %	42.92 ± 7.25

Hematological parameters revealed neutrophil predominance with a relatively low lymphocyte proportion, resulting in an elevated neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio. Total leukocyte and red cell indices were within the expected range, while platelet counts were normal.

Biochemical parameters showed mildly elevated fasting glucose and triglyceride levels, with corresponding TyG index values above normal. Lipid profile indicated borderline high LDL with reduced HDL. The mean ejection fraction was moderately reduced, consistent with left ventricular dysfunction.

Fig 1: Association between neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) with the severity of cardiac dysfunction.

Fig 2: Association between triglyceride–glucose (TyG) index with the severity of cardiac Dysfunction.

NLR positively correlated with (GRACE) risk score. ($r = 0.269$; $p = 0.02$). Even though Triglyceride Glucose Index was positively correlated with (GRACE) risk score, but not statistically significant.

The neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) demonstrated a significant positive correlation with the GRACE risk score ($r = 0.269$, $p = 0.02$), indicating that higher NLR values were associated with greater clinical risk and severity in STEMI patients. This finding supports the role of NLR as a reliable inflammatory marker reflecting adverse prognosis.

The triglyceride–glucose (TyG) index was also positively associated with the GRACE risk score; however, this relationship did not achieve statistical significance. This suggests that while metabolic stress, as reflected by the TyG index, may contribute to risk stratification, its predictive value in this cohort was less robust compared to NLR.

DISCUSSION

In the present study, we investigated the association of the triglyceride–glucose (TyG) index and the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) with the severity of cardiac dysfunction in patients presenting with acute ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI), as well as their relationship with the Global Registry of Acute Coronary Events (GRACE) risk score. Our findings demonstrated that NLR showed a significant positive correlation with the GRACE risk score, indicating its potential role as an inflammatory biomarker for short-term risk stratification. Although the TyG index also showed a positive association with GRACE scores, the relationship did not reach statistical significance in our cohort.

These findings are consistent with the growing body of evidence that highlights the interplay between metabolic dysfunction, systemic inflammation, and adverse outcomes in STEMI.^[17] Insulin resistance, often captured through the TyG index, has been shown to accelerate the

atherosclerotic process by impairing glucose and lipid metabolism, promoting endothelial dysfunction, and creating a prothrombotic state. Large-scale studies have reported that the TyG index is strongly associated with both the incidence and prognosis of cardiovascular disease, often outperforming traditional markers such as HOMA-IR.^[18] For instance, Wang et al. reported that in patients with acute coronary syndrome and diabetes, the TyG index independently predicted major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) over a 3-year follow-up.^[19] Similarly, Abdulhadi et al. observed that higher TyG values were proportionally linked with increased long-term cardiovascular risk in stable coronary artery disease.^[20] Although our study did not demonstrate a statistically significant association between TyG index and GRACE score, the positive trend aligns with these previous findings and suggests that a larger sample size or longer follow-up period may be necessary to clarify its predictive value.

Inflammation plays an equally critical role in the pathophysiology of STEMI.^[9] Following coronary blockage, neutrophils migrate quickly to the damaged heart tissue and worsen the injury through the release of enzymes, reactive oxygen compounds, and inflammatory molecules.^[10] Concurrently, lymphocyte counts decline in response to stress-induced cortisol release, tipping the balance toward a proinflammatory state. This imbalance between neutrophils and lymphocytes is captured by the NLR, which serves as a practical indicator of systemic inflammation.^[11] Our observation that elevated NLR correlates with higher GRACE risk scores is in agreement with earlier studies demonstrating its association with greater coronary artery disease burden, impaired left ventricular function, and higher incidence of MACE. This underscores the utility of NLR as a simple, cost-effective tool for bedside risk stratification in STEMI patients.^[13] The integration of NLR and TyG index with established prognostic tools such as the GRACE risk score may enhance risk prediction models in acute coronary syndromes.^[15,21] While the GRACE

score remains the gold standard, it primarily incorporates clinical and biochemical parameters without accounting for inflammatory or metabolic status. Adding easily available indices such as NLR and TyG could provide a more comprehensive assessment of patient risk, particularly in resource-limited settings where advanced biomarkers are not readily available.^[16,22] NLR, a new biomarker is a strong predictor of myocardial damage and myocardial dysfunction in STEMI patients.^[11] TyG can be used as a good prognostic indicator for myocardial damage.

Early assessment using NLR and TyG can be used to predict patient outcomes, as delayed diagnosis may lead to poorer prognosis. The changes in echocardiological measures and their co relations with these newer biomarkers improve prognostic value of clinical assessment, helping in better understanding of patients.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. Its retrospective and single-center design limits generalizability, and the relatively small sample size may have reduced the statistical power, particularly for detecting the association between TyG index and GRACE score. Furthermore, we did not evaluate long-term outcomes such as MACE, which could provide further insight into the prognostic value of these biomarkers. Future prospective, multicentred studies with larger cohorts and extended follow-up are warranted to validate our findings.

CONCLUSION

In summary, our study highlights the clinical relevance of simple inflammatory and metabolic markers in STEMI. NLR demonstrated a significant correlation with GRACE risk score, reinforcing its role as a prognostic biomarker. Although TyG index did not reach statistical significance, its positive trend suggests potential utility, particularly when integrated with established scoring systems. Incorporating such inexpensive and easily obtainable biomarkers into routine practice could enhance early risk stratification and improve individualized management of STEMI patients.

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